

RESULTS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF FOUR SKILLS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION Twenty-first century has become common and familiar to all people living on earth, because even though there are some differences in customs, cultures, and regions, English is used as a common language. English has common qualities. Because of this, it has been accepted as a global language among thousands of speakers of different languages. Due to the development of science and technology, great changes are taking place in human life everywhere in the world. Science, technology, business, education, travel, tourism etc. To stay, English serves as a common language and a global language. This language is used not only by scientists, business organizations and the Internet, but also in the fields of higher education and tourism. The results of its effectiveness in teaching are also important. This article covers the four skills of the English language about the results of the study.

Key words: global language, result and efficiency, oral proceedings, oral interactions, monologue speech, testing language.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЧЕТЫРЕХ НАВЫКОВ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

АННОТАЦИЯ Двадцать первый век стал общим и привычным для всех людей, живущих на земле, потому что, несмотря на некоторые различия в

обычаях, культурах и регионах, в качестве общего языка используется английский. У английского есть общие качества. Из-за этого он был признан глобальным языком среди тысяч носителей разных языков. В связи с развитием науки и техники в жизни людей повсюду в мире происходят большие изменения. Наука, технологии, бизнес, образование, путешествия, туризм и т. д. Английский язык служит общим языком и глобальным языком. Этот язык используют не только ученые, бизнес-организации и Интернет, но и в сфере высшего образования и туризма. Результаты его эффективности в обучении также важны. В этой статье рассматриваются четыре навыка английского языка о результатах исследования.

Ключевые слова: глобальный язык, результат и эффективность, устное производство, устное взаимодействие, монологическая речь, тестирование языка.

When we learn our native language, we first listen, then we speak, then we read, and finally we write. Listening, speaking, reading and writing are the four language skills that we need to develop in order to communicate effectively. Someone "fluent" in a language, we usually mean that they have a high level of all four skills. But as any teacher knows, students often have strengths or weaknesses in certain skills and in some cases can reach high levels , for example, in reading and writing, but cannot speak or listen at a comparable level.

The Common European Competence Framework expands the definition of communicative language skills to five skills and divides spoken language into two skills: oral production and oral interaction. This is based on evidence that the two skills are distinct, as one involves only monologue speech, while the other involves both speaker and listener speaking at the same time. Thus, the test for communicative speech should include both oral production and oral interaction.

A student's development of the four skills may be unbalanced, for example, a student may be strong in reading but weak in listening, writing or speaking. Cambridge English research shows that one of the main reasons ministries and school groups introduce Cambridge English exams is in that they test all four skills and, as a result, pay more attention to speaking and listening. It helps students develop communication skills in English.

Reference CAE certificate may be needed to work , study or move to another country : the US , Canada , Australia , the UK or Australia . Test results are accepted at such leading universities as Oxford University, University of Virginia, University of Toronto, McGill University. exam.

About 3 million people all over the world take the CAE exam every year. International certificates are the most prestigious in law, they are recognized by more than 13 thousand organizations: the majority of universities where teaching is conducted in English, employers, ministries of education of various countries.

today in several dozen authorized examination centers of the CAE, where you can not only prepare for exams, but also pass them. Classes in the centers are held both individually and in groups, which are divided depending on the level of training of students. Other international exams that testing in four skills:TOEFL (Test of English as a Foreign Language) , IELTS (International English Language Testing System), CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference) .

A study into the impact of Cambridge English exams in the state sector in Hebei province , Cambridge : Cambridge University Press , (2016) Investigating the impact of international assessment : A convergent parallel mixed methods approach , N (Eds) Second Language Assessment and Mixed Methods Research (Studies in Language Testing , volume 43) , Cambridge : Cambridge University Press (2012) An investigation into the effect of intensive language provision and external assessment in primary education .

Used literature:

1. Kakharov, K., & Azizov, Y. (2022). Mnemonics Techniques for Teaching English Language. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(11), 385-387.
2. Xusanboyevna, A. S. (2021, April). PRAGMATICS AND LINGVOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF SPEECH. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 23, No. 1, pp. 181-183).
3. Xusanboyevna, A. S. (2020, June). LINGUO-PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF SPEECH ACTS "EXPRESSION OF REFUSAL" IN RUSSIAN ENGLISH AND UZBEK. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 37-39).
4. Xusanboyevna, A. S. (2020, June). ROLE OF THE THEORY OF SPEECH ACTS IN THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC PRAGMATICS. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 43-45).
5. Азимова, Сайёра Хусанбоевна. "НУТҚ АКТЛАРИ ВА КОММУНИКАТИВ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯ: "РАД ЖАВОБИНИ БИЛДИРУВЧИ" ИЛЛОКАТЦИОН ҲАРАКАТНИ ПРАГМАТИК ТАҲЛИЛ ҚИЛИШ." *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА* 3.5 (2020).
6. Жаҳонгиров, Б. Б. (2022). ЎЗБЕКИСТОННИНГ ҲИНДИСТОН БИЛАН ИЛМИЙ ТЕХНИКАВИЙ АЛОҚАЛАРИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(5), 1058-1065.
7. Жаҳонгиров, Б. Б., & Турғунов, Т. А. (2021). ЎЗБЕКИСТОННИНГ ОСИЁ МАМЛАКАТЛАРИ БИЛАН ИЛМИЙ ТЕХНИКАВИЙ АЛОҚАЛАРИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(5), 1010-1021.
8. Turaboyeva, S. Z. (2022). О "ЎЗБЕК ВА ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛЛАРИДА" ДО "ST" КОНСЕРТИНИНГ СОЦИАЛ О "ЗИГА ХОСЛИГИ.
9. Turaboyeva, S. (2022). Jahon tilshunosligida lingvokulturologik birliklarning konseptual o'rganilishi.
10. Yuzboy ogli, R. A. (2022, April). ANGLIYA ELCHISI ALEKSANDR BYORNSNING BUXOROGA SAYOHATI TAFSILOTLARI. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 176-177).

11. Yuzboy o'g'li, R. A. (2022). ANTONY JENKINSON'S VISIT TO THE KHANATE OF BUKHARA AND THE LEADING ROLE OF THE KHANATE OF BUKHARA IN TRADE RELATIONS BETWEEN INDIA AND RUSSIA. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 19(1), 174-177.
12. Ubaydullayeva, D. (2022). ENGLISH LANGUAGE SYSTEMS AND PROBLEMS IN TEACHING THEM. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(11), 123-130.
13. Ubaydullaeva, D. (2022). PROBLEMS OF DESCRIPTION, CLASSIFICATION AND METATALOLOGY OF COMPLEX SENTENCES IN MODERN LINGUISTICS. *Science and Innovation*, 1(6), 560-564
14. Bazarova, D. (2022). VARIABILITY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 483-486.
15. Кахаров, Қ., & Абдусаломова, Г. (2022). ЧЕТ ТИЛИ ЎРГАНИШДА АХБОРОТ ВОСИТАЛАРИНИНГ РОЛИ. *ТА'ЛИМ ВА RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMİY JURNALI*, 2(10), 152-155.